

Using Vedic Tetrads to unlock and decipher the most difficult Buddhist Pali Sutta – Mulapariyayasutta

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Abstract:

The Mulapariyayasutta of Bhagavan Gautama Buddha has the distinction of being the most dense, difficult, abstruse and complicated texts of the Pali Canon. While the standard interpretation proposes twenty-four categories of existence, such an interpretation creates a chaotic situation where the categories are haphazard and non-linear. I draw upon my earlier Sanskrit reconstruction of the original sutra along with English translation and commentary to propose a completely novel hypothesis – the interpretation through the framework of the Vedas.

A new interpretation is proposed using the Advaita Vedanta model, by which the twenty-four states are grouped as tetrads. This method elegantly condenses the 24 categories into six levels of four Dhyanas (Jhanas) each. This is even more proof that Bhagavan Gautama Buddha teachings were in complete sync with classical Vedic thought. The differences that future Buddhist thinkers proposed were a departure from original Vedic focus.

Keywords:

Mulapariyayasutta, Pali Canon, Pali Sutras, Pali Suttas, Vedic Tetrads, Gautama Buddha, Advaita Vedanta, Vedas

Introduction:

The Mulapariyayasutta is a mix of elements (Panchabhutas), denizens in each loka, quality of the loka, abode or seat of each loka, senses and essence. The state of Nirvana is the final category listed under essences. Such a miscellaneous mixing of dissimilar and unlike categories as superior to the other categories creates a lot of confusion for the seeker. It is difficult to understand how the twenty-four categories can be ranked one above the other. Hence, the message of the Mulapariyayasutta is easily lost.

The problems of the standard interpretation:

I list some of the peculiarities of the traditional interpretation. The verses are as per my Sanskrit reconstruction of the Sutra.¹

- 1) Why are qualities ranked above elements and senses above abodes?
- 2) Why does Gautama Buddha differentiate between Prajapathi and the Brahman in verses 7 and 8?
- 3) Why does Gautama Buddha invoke Brahman in verse 8 and then invoke qualities, abodes, senses and essences as superior to the Brahman?
- 4) Why does Gautama Buddha refer to yoga in verse 25?
- 5) Why does the Sutta close with the strange words, "They (te), the Bhikshus (bhikshava) of the Bhagavan (bhagavatha) applauded (abhinandan) not (na) the discourse (bhaashitham)?" What is the reason for rejection?
- 6) What is the meaning of Ekatvam, Nanatvam, Sarvam and Nirvanam in verses 21-24?
- 7) Thanissaro Bhikkhu proposes that this Sutta was meant to disprove the Sankhya philosophers?² Is that true?
- 8) In Buddha's final Nirvana as explained in the Mahaparinibbana Sutta, upon leaving his mortal body, the four abodes get prominence over all others. None of the other Tetrads are mentioned. In this Sutta, the 4 senses and 4 essences are superior to the 4 abodes. Why is there a discrepancy?

Hypothesis:

A tetrad model of interpretation classifying the twenty-four categories into six levels of four Dhyanas (Jhanas) each, makes perfect sense for both Buddhist and Vedic scholars. Important findings are revealed which fit perfectly with the Vedic cosmogony, suggesting that Gautama Buddha taught exactly what the Vedas proposed and not a different worldview.

I propose a new category of tetrads to come up with a unique Vedic interpretation of Gautama Buddha's teachings in this Sutta. The resulting model is listed on the next page. I will analyze the model after the diagram.

The Six Tetrads of Dhyana (Sanskrit)

State of Yoga	Effects of Yoga					
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Level 6
Dhyana	Element	Denizen	Quality	Abode	Sense	Essence
Prathama	Prithvi	Bhu	Aabasvara	Akasa Ananta Ayatanam	Drishtam	Ekatvam
Dvithiya	Apa	Deva	Shubhkritsna	Vigyana Ananta Ayatanam	Shrutam	Nanathvam
Trithiya	Teja	Prajapathi	Brihatphala	Akinchana Ayatanam	Matham	Sarvam
Chaturthiya	Vayu	Brahman	Abhibhu	Na Samjna Asamjna Ayatanam	Vignatham	Nirvanam

The Six Tetrads of Dhyana (English)

State of Yoga	Effects of Yoga					
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Level 6
Jhana	Element	Denizen	Quality	Abode	Sense	Essence
1	Earth	Living beings	Complete radiance	The altar of the infinite sky	Sight	Singularity (ego)
2	Divine waters	Deva	Complete goodness	The altar of infinite knowledge	Hearing	Many
3	Fire	Prajapathi	Greatest fruit	The altar of not-anything	Understanding	All
4	Air	Brahman	Supreme manifestation	The altar of neither understanding nor non-understanding	Knowledge	Nirvana

Arguments and discussion:

The first clue to unlocking the puzzle emerges when the word Brahman emerges in verse 8. Pali has a big problem with the term – Brahman. It fails to capture the difference between Prajapathi Brahma and Brahman. This problem disappears in my reconstructed Sanskrit Sutra where the word Brahman is used in the neuter form and not as Brahma. Any scholar who understands Vedas or Upanishads knows that this is a critical difference. Pali scholars fail to see the difference. For example, Thanissaro Bhikkhu does not differentiate between “Pajapathi” and “Brahma” in his translation.³

Vedic scholars know that Prajapathi and Brahma are the same, and this is why Prajapathi is called Prajapathi Brahma. The word Brahma is used in the masculine form to denote Prajapathi.

Vedic scholars call the highest manifestation of the Atman as Brahm or as Brahman. Gautama Buddha clearly differentiates the two states, hence arguing that both are the same is blatantly wrong. Gautama Buddha goes further. He argues that the Brahman is superior to Prajapathi as a higher state. This hierarchy can only be explained by the neuter Brahman and by resorting to Vedic cosmology of the Atman-Brahman as the creator of Prajapathi.

The twenty-four states are but linked together in groups of four.

Hence, verses 1,5,9,13,17 and 21 are connected together with similar characteristics.

Similarly, 2,6,10,14,18 and 22 are connected together.

Similarly, 3,7,11,15,19 and 23 are connected together.

Similarly, 4,8,12,16,20 and 24 are connected together.

Let us examine the four cross references.

- 1) **Cross references to Dhyana 1:** The first level of meditation (Dhyana) is about earth or Prithvi loka. Earth is where living beings exist. By gaining earth, one gains over all living beings (level 2). This can be done only by inner purification that leads to inner radiance within. This inner radiance when perfected is level 3. When a seeker gains mastery over earth, he no longer belongs to earth, but to the sky that covers it. Dyau-Prithvi is a Vedic combine, if you leave one you attain the other. The infinite sky is thus level 4. The altar of the infinite sky is the Vedic altar on earth, where one sacrifices his attachments to the body. Level 3 and 4 is achieved by mastery over sight, which represents Prithvi. One has to triumph over their singular ego to gain mastery of all levels in Dhyana 1.
- 2) **Cross references to Dhyana 2:** The second level of meditation (Dhyana) is about Aapa (the divine waters) that flow from Svarga to earth. It refers to the beginning of Atma Gyana. Aapa emerges from Deva loka, inhabited by the Devas. Hence, Devas are level 2. The Devas are characterized by complete goodness (level 3). A human can therefore become a Deva by slaying the Asuric qualities within himself. The altar of infinite knowledge is the altar of the mind, where Atma Gyana emerges. Atma Gyana is the infinite knowledge sought by all beings. Hearing (level 5) refers to Shruti (the heard Vedas). Vedas bring Atma Gyana. When one gains control of hearing along with sight in Dhyana 1, the external world is completely conquered. Sight and hearing are the two predominant ways in which the external world influences us. In level 6, the multiplicity of the universe is surpassed. One realizes the beginning of Advaita, that the universe and the Self (Atman) are both the same.
- 3) **Cross references to Dhyana 3:** The third level of meditation (Dhyana) is about Prajapathi Brahma. Proficient Vedic scholars call Prajapathi Brahma as Prajapathi to

avoid confusion with the Brahman. This is exactly what Gautama Buddha has done. The fire is sacrifice and Prajapathi is attained only by sacrifice of all inner desires. When the seeker becomes Prajapathi by sacrifice and inner purification, he becomes Prajapathi himself. This is the greatest fruit, referred to as level 3. This altar of sacrifice is where everything is sacrificed and nothing (not-anything) is left. This is level 4. This state of Prajapathi can be obtained only by the highest understanding of Advaita – that there is no two. The entire universe collapses into the creator Prajapathi which the seeker becomes.

- 4) **Cross references to Dhyana 4:** The fourth level of meditation (Dhyana) is about Vayu or Air. Vayu is considered as a Marut and the child of Bhagavan Shiva. Hence, both fall into the same realm. Vayu is level 1 and Brahman (Shiva) is level 2. The Brahman is the highest manifestation and the most supreme. Everything ends with the Brahman or Atman in the Vedas. The same applies to Gautama Buddha. By borrowing the idea of Brahman, he shows us that attaining the Brahman is indeed the highest goal. The nature of the Brahman is Nirguna – without any essential characteristics that the seeker can understand. Hence, the Brahman cannot be understood or not-understood (level 4). The Brahman reveals himself to the seeker. It is an experience that cannot be described in words. This is a realm of infinite and pure knowledge (level 5). This is a state of Nirvana (level 6) where all understanding ceases and one becomes united in yoga with the creator Brahman. Brahman is the source of even Prajapathi.

Now, let us examine the six levels one after the other.

- 1) The order of level 1 emerges from the Taittiriya Upanishad 2.1.1 which states, “From the Atman, Akasha emerged. From Akasha, Vayu emerged. From Vayu, Agni (Tejas) emerged. From Agni, Aapa emerged. From Aapa, Prithvi emerged.” Gautama Buddha clearly read the Taittiriya Upanishad and quoted the origin of the Panchabhutas in precisely the same order. In order for a seeker to become one with the Brahman, he has to retrace the path. He has to go from Prithvi to Aapa to Tejas to Vayu.
- 2) The order of level 2 emerges from the Mandukya Upanishad which talks of the four realms of existence. The first state of Vaisva is the waking state inhabited by humans. The fourth state of Turiya is that of the Brahman. Gautama Buddha introduces a change with the second state of dreams and third states of deep sleep. In the Mandukya Upanishad, the two states refer to mind and Devas. Gautama Buddha refers the second and third state to Devas and Prajapathi.
- 3) The order of level 3 is about mastery of the human, Deva, Prajapathi and Brahman states. The inner light of the human is called "complete radiance." The Deva are characterized by complete goodness as compared to the complete evil exemplified by the Asuras. The status of Prajapathi is the greatest fruit possible to the seeker. Prajapathi is the last of the external manifestations of the Brahman. The final state is that of the Brahman who is also called Shiva or Vishnu. This is the highest or supreme manifestation.
- 4) The order of level 4 is about mastery of abodes. One masters the earth to gain the "infinite sky." One masters the sky and attains "infinite knowledge." The realm of Prajapathi is beyond all materiality. Hence all materialism of the world has to be sacrificed in the sacrificial yajna to get there. The Brahman is a state beyond comprehension and non-comprehension. It is a state of pure experience.
- 5) The order of level 5 is about mastery of senses. Sight is linked to Prithvi (earth). Hearing (meaning hearing the Vedas) is linked to Atma Gyan and discovering the

Devas within. Note that Devas and Vedas (shruthi) rhyme with each other. Prajapathi is the highest understanding. Brahman is the highest knowledge. As we see, each level is linked to the earlier level and goes deeper into the essential characteristic at each state of Dhyana (Jhana).

- 6) The order of level 6 is about mastery of essences. The realm of singularity has to be conquered, meaning that the ego (which assumes that it is the centre of the universe) has to be conquered. The realm of Devas is of multiplicity of goodness. Multiplicity has to be conquered by Atma Gyana and Advaita. One has to realize the oneness behind the Devas. Prajapathi is everything. He is both good and evil, he became the Devas and Asuras. When one understands the true nature of Prajapathi, one realizes that one is the universe and that one is all (sarvam). The final state of Nirvana has no description because it is the realm of the Brahman.

Additional arguments:

Now we can answer the eight questions raised on the beginning.

- 1) Why are qualities ranked above elements and senses above abodes?
We now realize that each tetrad is in the same category as the others. They represent different levels within the same 4 Jhanas. Hence, every tetrad is interdependent on each other. Looking at one tetrad as superior to another is a wrong perspective.
- 2) Why does Gautama Buddha differentiate between Prajapathi and the Brahman in verses 7 and 8?
Vedic philosophy differentiates clearly between Prajapathi and Brahman. They are not the same. Since Gautama Buddha was advocating the lost Vedic philosophy, he too differentiated between Prajapathi and Brahman. Acceptance of the Brahman indicates that the system taught by Gautama Buddha was no different from the Vedas and Upanishads. Since all commentators assume that Hindu and Buddhist views are different, they land themselves in a conundrum. They cannot explain why Buddha refers to the Vedic Brahman. This is a big loophole in traditional understanding that cannot be wished away.
- 3) Why does Gautama Buddha invoke Brahman in verse 8 and then invoke qualities, abodes, senses and essences as superior to the Brahman?
When analyzed from the Tetrad perspective, there is nothing superior to the Brahman. Even the state of Nirvana is the state of the Brahman. Analyzing the 24 states together causes immense confusion, however the breaking into 6 Tetrads solves every problem.
- 4) Why does Gautama Buddha refer to yoga in verse 25?
Jhana or Dhyana is a form of yoga. The Vedas and Upanishads talk of 4 yogas – Gyana, Dhyana, Karma and Bhakthi. The Tetrad is a reference to the 4 Jhanas. This is why Gautama Buddha refers to yoga in verse 25.
- 5) Why does the Sutta close with the strange words, “They (te), the Bhikshus (bhikshava) of the Bhagavan (bhagavatha) applauded (abhinandan) not (na) the discourse (bhaashitham)?” What is the reason for rejection?
The true inner message of the Vedas was lost well before Gautama Buddha existed. Rishi Shaunaka and Yaska talk of how Vedic knowledge was completely lost even during their times, which was well before Buddha. They created books like

Brhaddevata and Nirukta to save whatever little Vedic knowledge was left behind. Hence, it is safe to say that by the time of Gautama Buddha, true Vedic knowledge had disappeared and was replaced by mindless ritualists following a corrupted Purva Mimamsa view. The monks listening to Gautama Buddha were also likely to have been mindless ritualists. For ritualists, talking of inner purification was blasphemy. This is why the Bhikshus rejected Buddha's message of inner purification.

6) What is the meaning of Ekatvam, Nanatvam, Sarvam and Nirvanam in verses 21-24? The four terms refer to rejection of the ego, rejection of the world of multiplicity, accepting the Advaita everywhere, and realizing that the final state is beyond words. The final state, Nirvana, is beyond the senses and mind. Hence, it is a state of complete cessation.

7) Thanissaro Bhikkhu proposes that this Sutta was meant to disprove the Sankhya philosophers?⁴ Is that true? Such a hypothesis assumes that there was a confrontational approach between Buddha and the Vedic philosophers. I have shown that the converse is true. Buddha taught the philosophy distilled from the Vedas and Upanishads. He used a different set of terms to appeal to the lay audience who did not understand Sanskrit and the Vedic terminology. Hence, disproving the Sankhya philosophers is absolutely incorrect. However, there is a hint that Gautama Buddha was opposing the mindless ritualists who had forgotten the inner purification and Atma Gyana.

8) In Buddha's final Nirvana as explained in the Mahaparinibbana Sutta, upon leaving his mortal body, the four abodes get prominence over all others. None of the other Tetrads are mentioned. In this Sutta, the 4 senses and 4 essences are superior to the 4 abodes. Why is there a discrepancy? During the final Nirvana, we see that there is a description of the 4 Jhanas and the 4 abodes (level 4). It is not that the Tetrad of the abodes is superior to all other five Tetrads. All of them are equivalent and each level talks about a separate grouping. Hence, this is further proof that each tetrad is equivalent to the other. Talking of one Tetrad is the same as talking of any of the other five Tetrads.

Conclusion:

We have showed that the Tetrad model of Vedic Advaita can break down the extremely complex cosmology of Mulapariyayasutta into a simple set of six Vedic Tetrads. These Tetrads align perfectly with Vedic cosmology and the earliest Buddhist cosmology. They reveal that there was almost no difference between Vedic and the earliest Buddhist worldviews.

References:

¹ Aravindakshan, V. (2026). Lost Sanskrit Reconstruction, Translation and Commentary on the most difficult Buddhist Pali Sutta - Mulapariyayasutta. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20142642>

² Thanissaro Bhikkhu (Trans.). (1998). Mulapariyaya Sutta: The root sequence (MN 1). Access to Insight. <https://www.accesstoinsight.org/tipitaka/mn/mn.001.than.html>

³ Ibid.

⁴ Thanissaro Bhikkhu (Trans.). (1998). *Mulapariyaya Sutta: The root sequence (MN 1)*. Access to Insight. <https://www.accesstoinsight.org/tipitaka/mn/mn.001.than.html>